

Synthesis and spectral study of yttrium and lanthanide chloride complexes of 2,3-dimethyl-4-formyl(benzhydrazide)-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one

G. Ajithkumar and P. K. Radhakrishnan*

School of Chemical Sciences, Mahatma Gandhi University, Kottayam-686 560, Kerala, India

E-mail : pkrkn@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : A series of complexes of the Schiff base, 2,3-dimethyl-4-formyl(benzhydrazide)-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one (L) of the general composition $[LnL_2Cl_2]Cl$ (where Ln = Y, La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Dy, Ho or Er) has been synthesized and characterized. L acts as a neutral ligand donating through both the carbonyl oxygens and the azomethine nitrogen in these complexes. Two chloride ions are coordinated in the complexes. A coordination number of eight is assigned to the metal ion in all the complexes.

Keywords : Synthesis, yttrium, lanthanide, complex, Schiff base.

Introduction

In continuation of our earlier investigations on the pyrazolone derived Schiff bases and its rare earth complexes^{1,2}, here we report the synthesis and characterization of an antipyrene derived Schiff base and its complexes with yttrium and some lanthanide chlorides. Antipyrene and its derivatives were shown to have antibacterial, anti-inflammatory and antifungal properties and these physiological properties may vary on complexation with metal ions³⁻⁶. The ligand L (Fig. 1) and the complexes would be expected to be of aforementioned physiological importance.

Fig. 1. 2,3-Dimethyl-4-formyl(benzhydrazide)-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one (L).

Experimental

Antipyrene-4-carboxaldehyde and benzhydrazide were purchased from Aldrich, USA. Yttrium and lanthanide chlorides were prepared by dissolving the respective oxides (99.9%) (Rare Earths Ltd., Kerala or Aldrich, USA) in 60% AR hydrochloric acid (Merck). The crystals of the metal chlorides were obtained by evaporating the solution using a steam bath. The solvents used were either GPR or AR grade (Merck, India; BDH, India or SRL, India). The Schiff base L and the complexes were analyzed for the elements carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen on a Heraeus CHNO rapid analyzer. The metal content was estimated gravimetrically as oxides⁷ and the chloride content by Volhard's method⁸. The molar conductance in DMF, methanol and nitrobenzene (10^{-3} M solutions) were measured at room temperature using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge with a dip-type cell of platinum electrodes (cell constant 1.1008). The IR spectrum of the Schiff base and the complexes were recorded in the range $4000-400$ cm^{-1} on a Shimadzu IR 470 spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra in solid state (paste with Nujol) and in solution (10^{-3} M DMF and methanol) were recorded in the range 200-1100 nm on a Shimadzu UV 160A spectrophotometer. The ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX-500 spectrometer using DMSO-*d*₆ as solvent.

Preparation of 2,3-dimethyl-4-formyl(benzhydrazide)-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one (L) :

10 mmol of benzhydrazide (1.362 g) in ethanol (20 ml) was mixed with few drops of HCl to maintain the pH at 6 and refluxed on a steam bath. 10 mmol of antipyrine-4-carboxaldehyde (2.162 g) in ethanol (30 ml) was added to the above solution and refluxed for about 6 h. The pale yellow crystals obtained after cooling were washed with cold ethanol to remove the unreacted reactants, if any. It was then recrystallised from ethyl acetate and dried over phosphorus(v) oxide under reduced pressure. The purity was checked by TLC, infrared spectrum and elemental analyses.

Preparation of the complexes :

1 mmol of the metal chloride in ethanol (10 ml) was added to a boiling solution of 2.1 mmol of the Schiff base (0.702 g) in ethanol (20 ml) and kept under reflux for about 4 h. The crystalline solid complex formed on cooling was filtered and washed with isopropanol and hot benzene subsequently to remove any excess of reactants. It was then recrystallised from methanol and dried over phosphorus(v) oxide under vacuum.

Results and discussion

From the elemental analyses results (Table 1), the complexes may be formulated as LnL_2Cl_3 ($\text{Ln} = \text{Y, La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Dy, Ho or Er}$). They are non-hygroscopic solids soluble in acetone, acetonitrile, DMF, DMSO, ethanol, isopropanol, methanol and nitrobenzene but insoluble in benzene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, ethyl acetate, toluene and water.

Table 1. Analytical data of complexes (calculated values in parentheses)

Sl. no.	Complex	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)		Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)
		Metal	Chloride		
1.	[YL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	10.31 (10.29)	12.29 (12.31)	85	260
2.	[LaL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	15.23 (15.20)	11.61 (11.64)	82	265
3.	[PrL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	15.38 (15.38)	11.60 (11.61)	80	263
4.	[NdL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	15.72 (15.69)	11.55 (11.57)	84	268
5.	[SmL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	16.30 (16.25)	11.45 (11.49)	78	269
6.	[EuL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	16.40 (16.39)	11.46 (11.47)	90	272
7.	[GdL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	16.90 (16.87)	11.35 (11.40)	81	270
8.	[DyL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	17.36 (17.33)	11.31 (11.34)	80	273
9.	[HoL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	17.59 (17.54)	11.26 (11.31)	86	275
10.	[ErL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	17.76 (17.75)	11.26 (11.29)	88	278

The observed values of the electrical conductance of the complexes in three non aqueous solvents, viz. DMF ($67\text{--}70 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$), methanol ($93\text{--}96 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) and nitrobenzene ($25\text{--}27 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) are in good agreement with the results of Geary⁹, and suggest 1 : 1 electrolytic behaviors for all the complexes. Thus the complexes may be formulated as : $[\text{LnL}_2\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{Y, La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Dy, Ho or Er}$).

IR spectra :

The Schiff base L shows two strong IR absorption bands at 1668 and 1628 cm^{-1} which are attributed to the $\text{C}=\text{O}_{(19)}$ and $\text{C}=\text{O}_{(18)}$ stretching vibrations respectively¹⁰⁻¹². In complexes, these bands are shifted to 1635 and 1575 cm^{-1} respectively indicating the coordination¹⁰ of both the carbonyl oxygens. The band at 1565 cm^{-1} due to $\text{C}=\text{N}$ stretching vibration in L is shifted to $\sim 1555 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ showing the coordination¹³⁻¹⁶ of azomethine nitrogen. Thus the ligand appears to be tridentate. The $\nu(\text{M}-\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$ stretching vibrations are observed around 498 and 435 cm^{-1} respectively¹⁴. The far infrared spectra of the complexes show a band in the range $310\text{--}315 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is attributed¹⁷ to the $\text{M}-\text{Cl}$ stretching vibration. This, along with molar conductance data, confirms that two of the chloride ions are coordinated.

Electronic spectra :

The absorption spectrum of the ligand L shows two maxima at 41407 and 27173 cm^{-1} which corresponds to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow n^*$ transitions respectively¹⁸. In complexes, these bands are shifted to the regions $39344\text{--}41365$ and $24384\text{--}26692 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. The $f-f$ bands are observed only in the case of Pr^{III} , Nd^{III} , Sm^{III} , Dy^{III} , Ho^{III} and Er^{III} complexes and for other lanthanide complexes, the bands could not be identified as they are presumably masked by the ligand charge transfer transitions¹⁹⁻²¹. The $f-f$ transition frequencies along with tentative assignments^{22,23} are given in Table 2. The covalency parameters suggest weak covalent character²⁴ to the metal-ligand bond. The spectral profile of hypersensitive bands of Nd^{III} , Ho^{III} and Er^{III} complexes closely resembles that of eight coordinated complexes reported by Karrakar^{25,26} and is in good agreement with the other physico-chemical investigations. The spectral features of complexes are similar both in the solid state and in solution (DMF and methanol), indicating the identical stoichiometry and coordination number in solid as well as in solution phase.

Table 2. *f-f* Transitions of the chloride complexes of Pr, Nd, Sm, Dy, Ho and Er with L

Complex	Abs. max (cm ⁻¹)	Molar extinction coefficients ^e (ε)		Tentative assignments	Bonding parameters
		DMF	MeOH		
[PrL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	22435	14.04	14.12	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₂	β = 0.9968
	21230	5.47	5.54	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₁	b ^{1/2} = 0.0400
	20697	8.74	8.90	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₀	δ = 0.3210
	16785	11.82	11.87	³ H ₄ → ¹ D ₂	η = 0.0016
[NdL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	19531	1.95	2.10	⁴ I _{9/2} → ⁴ G _{9/2}	β = 0.9969
	13386	7.49	8.01	⁴ I _{9/2} → ⁴ G _{7/2}	b ^{1/2} = 0.0394
	12531	16.07	16.22	⁴ I _{9/2} → ⁴ F _{5/2}	δ = 0.3110
	11494	10.46	10.93	⁴ I _{9/2} → ⁴ F _{3/2}	η = 0.0016
[SmL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	24096	2.98	3.06	⁶ H _{5/2} → (⁶ P, ⁴ P) _{5/2}	β = 0.9969
	21052	11.31	11.97	⁶ H _{5/2} → ⁴ I _{11/2}	b ^{1/2} = 0.0394
	20491	17.43	17.91	⁶ H _{5/2} → ⁴ M _{15/2}	δ = 0.3110
	10482	8.27	8.75	⁶ H _{5/2} → ⁴ F _{11/2}	η = 0.0016
[DyL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	25839	18.36	18.77	⁶ H _{15/2} → ⁶ I _{13/2}	β = 0.9882
	22172	3.65	4.01	⁶ H _{15/2} → ⁶ I _{15/2}	b ^{1/2} = 0.7113
	13245	8.13	8.46	⁶ H _{15/2} → ⁶ I _{3/2}	δ = 1.1941
	12315	9.16	9.50	⁶ H _{15/2} → ⁶ F _{5/2}	η = 0.0059
[HoL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	10986	11.59	11.83	⁶ H _{15/2} → ⁶ F _{7/2}	
	23696	18.36	18.77	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ G ₃	β = 0.9882
	22075	13.62	13.91	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ G ₅	b ^{1/2} = 0.0406
	21097	4.46	4.52	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ F ₂	δ = 0.3311
	20533	7.19	7.40	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ F ₃	η = 0.0017
[ErL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	18587	15.13	15.46	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ F ₄	
	15503	14.97	15.10	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ F ₅	
	24570	12.31	12.46	⁴ I _{15/2} → (² G, ⁴ F) _{9/2}	β = 0.9918
	20533	2.31	2.49	⁴ I _{15/2} → ⁴ F _{7/2}	b ^{1/2} = 0.064
	19230	12.70	12.84	⁴ I _{15/2} → ⁴ H _{11/2}	δ = 0.8268
	18484	9.16	9.27	⁴ I _{15/2} → ⁴ S _{3/2}	η = 0.0040
	15243	4.83	4.98	⁴ I _{15/2} → ⁴ F _{9/2}	

¹H NMR spectra :

The ¹H NMR resonance signals of the ligand L and its yttrium as well as lanthanum complexes at room temperature are presented in Table 3 along with their assignments. The coordination through azomethine nitrogen^{27,28} is confirmed since the (-N=C-H) singlet at 8.42 ppm is shifted to 8.02 ppm in yttrium and lanthanum complexes. The broad multiplets in the region 7.23–7.67 and 7.53–7.79 ppm are attributable to the phenyl protons of pyrazolone and hydrazide moieties respectively and their shifts to the regions 7.20–7.62 and 7.54–7.98 ppm respectively indicate the coordination²⁰ of both the carbonyl oxygens.

Table 3. ¹H NMR spectral data (ppm) of L and its complexes with yttrium and lanthanum chlorides

L	[YL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	[LaL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	Assignment
2.53	2.53	2.53	C—CH ₃ 13
3.35	3.35	3.35	N—CH ₃ 12
8.42	8.02	8.02	N=C—H 14
11.29	8.21	8.24	N—N—H 16a
7.67	7.62	7.62	
7.46	7.20	7.20	
7.23	7.21	7.21	
7.46	7.22	7.22	
7.67	7.62	7.62	

Table-3 (contd)

7.76	7.98	7.98
7.79	7.67	7.67
7.53	7.54	7.54
7.79	7.65	7.65
7.77	7.98	7.98

¹³C NMR spectra :

The ¹³C NMR of L as well as its yttrium and lanthanide complexes are presented in Table 4. The resonance signal at 144.35 ppm in L due to C₍₁₄₎ is shifted to 124.91 ppm in complexes showing the coordination of azomethine nitrogen and the shifts of C₍₅₎ and C₍₁₇₎ to 166.35 and 164.51 ppm respectively indicate the coordination of both the carbonyl oxygen atoms²⁹⁻³¹.

Table 4. ¹³C NMR spectral data (ppm) of L and its complexes with yttrium and lanthanum chlorides

L	[YL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	[LaL ₂ Cl ₂]Cl	Assignment
8.13	8.13	8.13	C—CH ₃ 13
37.62	37.60	37.60	N—CH ₃ 12
144.35	124.90	124.90	N=C—H 14
161.30	161.30	161.30	
109.20	100.04	100.05	
164.80	166.35	166.35	
147.26	147.26	147.26	
123.28	125.36	125.36	
130.69	127.62	127.62	
126.47	126.61	126.61	
130.69	127.62	127.62	
123.28	125.31	125.31	
168.47	164.51	164.51	
132.49	131.24	131.24	
127.67	138.32	138.32	
129.35	129.97	129.97	
134.47	133.04	133.04	
129.35	129.97	129.97	
127.67	138.32	138.32	

On the basis of analytical and spectral data the tentative structure of the complexes may be assigned as follows (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. [LnL₂Cl₂]Cl (Ln = Y, La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Dy, Ho or Er).

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